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PERINATAL INVOLVEMENT OF CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM AND ITS IMPACT ON CHILD DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the relationship between perinatal lesions of the central nervous system and neurological syndromes formed in childhood with disorders of somatic development was studied. Children and adolescents treated at the neurological rehabilitation center were selected as the object of observation. The study was conducted retrospectively based on the data of 110 children under 2 years of age, recorded at the time of hospitalization. All of them had perinatal CNS damage or associated neurological syndromes. Anthropometric indicators were assessed using z-points in accordance with statistical standards. Results: Signs of perinatal damage manifested in the developmental process of a significant number of children.

Short stature, weight deficit, and head circumference anomalies were common. In some children, macrocephaly or height was noted. Restriction of motor activity was also most often observed in children with perinatal lesions. Conclusion: Perinatal damage to the central nervous system significantly affects the process of growth and development of children. The pathology manifests itself through various disorders, hindering the child's overall quality of life and social integration. Consequently, the early detection of this pathology and the application of complex treatment methods are necessary for the health of children.

Keywords: central nervous system, perinatal involvement, developmental disorders, pediatric neurology

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MARKAZIY ASAB TIZIMINING PERINATAL ZARARLANISHI VA UNING BOLALAR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur ishda markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi va bolalik davrida shakllanadigan nevrologik sindromlarning somatik rivojlanishdagi buzilishlar bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi

o'rganildi. Kuzatuv obyekti sifatida nevrologik reabilitatsiya markazida davolangan bolalar va o'smirlar tanlandi. Tadqiqot 2 yoshgacha bo'lgan 110 nafar bemor bolalarning shifoxonaga yotqizilish vaqtida qayd etilgan ma'lumotlari asosida retrospektiv ravishda olib borildi. Ularning barchasida markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi yoki unga aloqador nevrologik sindromlar mavjud edi. Antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar statistik standartlarga muvofiq ravishda z-ballar orqali baholandi. Natijalar: Perinatal zararlanish belgilari bolalarning sezilarli qismining rivojlanish jarayonida namoyon bo'ldi. Ko'pincha past bo'y, vazn yetishmovchiligi va bosh atrofi anomaliyalari uchradi. Ba'zi bolalarda esa makrosefaliya yoki baland bo'y qayd etildi. Harakat faoliyatining cheklanishi ham ko'pincha perinatal zararlanishga duch kelgan bolalarda kuzatildi. Xulosa: Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi bolalarning o'sish va rivojlanish jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Patologiya turli buzilishlar orqali namoyon bo'lib, bolaning umumiy hayot sifati va ijtimoiy integratsiyasini qiyinlashtiradi. Demak, ushbu patologiyani erta aniqlash va kompleks davolash usullarini qo'llash bolalar salomatligi uchun zarurdir.

Kalit so'zlar: markaziy asab tizimi, perinatal zararlanish, rivojlanish buzilishlari, bolalar nevrologiyasi

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ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНОЕ ПОРАЖЕНИЕ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА РАЗВИТИЕ ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной работе изучена взаимосвязь перинатального поражения центральной нервной системы и неврологических синдромов, формирующихся в детском возрасте, с нарушениями соматического развития. В качестве объекта наблюдения были выбраны дети и подростки, находившиеся на лечении в центре неврологической реабилитации. Исследование проводилось ретроспективно на основании данных, зафиксированных при поступлении в стационар у 110 больных детей в возрасте до 2 лет. Все они имели перинатальное поражение центральной нервной системы или связанные с ним неврологические синдромы. Антропометрические показатели оценивались с помощью z-баллов в соответствии со статистическими стандартами. Результаты: Признаки перинатального поражения проявлялись в процессе развития значительной части детей. Чаще встречались низкий рост, дефицит массы тела и аномалии окружности головы.

У некоторых детей отмечалась макроцефалия или высокий рост. Ограничение двигательной активности также чаще наблюдалось у детей с перинатальным поражением. Заключение: Перинатальное поражение центральной нервной системы оказывает существенное влияние на процесс роста и развития детей. Патология проявляется различными нарушениями, которые затрудняют общее качество жизни и социальную интеграцию ребенка. Следовательно, раннее выявление данной патологии и применение комплексных методов лечения необходимо для здоровья детей.

Ключевые слова: центральная нервная система, перинатальное поражение, нарушения развития, детская неврология

Kirish: Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi homila yoki yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq davrida yuzaga keladigan turli patogen omillar ta'sirida shakllanadigan patologik jarayon sifatida izohlanadi. Bunday holat ko'pincha ensefalopatiya, motor funksiyalarning buzilishi, kognitiv qiyinchiliklar va xulq-atvor o'zgarishlari bilan birga kechadi. Natijada, bolaning ta'lim olish, rivojlanish va ijtimoiy moslashuv imkoniyatlari cheklanadi. Patologiyaning etiologiyasi xilma-xil bo'lib, unga homiladorlik davrida gipoksiya, infeksiyalar, tug'ruqdagi jarohatlar, erta tug'ilish va boshqa xavf omillari kiradi. Ushbu jarayon neyronlarning rivojlanishi va markaziy asab tizimining yetilishida jiddiy uzilishlarga sabab bo'ladi. Bu esa asab tizimi buzilishi bilan bog'liq klinik belgilarni

yuzaga keltiradi. Somatik rivojlanishdagi asosiy buzilishlar tana o'Ichamlarining anomaliyalari (mikrosefaliya yoki makrosefaliya), o'sishning sekinlashuvi yoki tezlashuvi, shuningdek, tana vazni va bo'y nisbatining nomutanosibligi ko'rinishida namoyon bo'ladi. Bu ko'rsatkichlarni aniqlashda antropometrik metodlar keng qo'llaniladi. Perinatal zararlanish bilan bog'liq rivojlanish buzilishlari ijtimoiy kamsirishlar xavfini kuchaytiradi, bu esa bolaning psixologik holati va ijtimoiy moslashuviga salbiy ta'sir qiladi. Demak, kasallikni erta aniqlash va kompleks reabilitatsiya usullarini qo'llash bolalar rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal davridagi zararlanishi bilan bog'liq nevrologik buzilishlar o'rtasidagi aloqani aniqlash, shuningdek, ushbu omillarning bolalar somatik rivojlanishiga ta'sirini baholashdan iborat. Shuningdek, tadqiqotda perinatal zararlanishning bolalar rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi degan taxmin ilgari suriladi.

Materiallar va metodlar: Tadqiqot davomida 2023-2024-yillarda statsionar sharoitda davolangan bemorlar klinik hujjatlar asosida qayta ko'rib chiqildi. Unda 1 oylikdan 2 yoshgacha bo'lgan 110 nafar bola va o'smir ishtirok etdi. Ularning barchasida markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi yoki unga bog'liq nevrologik sindromlar mavjud edi. Bolalarning yoshi o'rtacha $9,7 \pm 4,3$ yilni ko'rsatdi, ulardan 69 nafari (56,3%) o'g'il bolalar va 41 nafari (43,7%) qiz bolalar edi. Tadqiqotga faqat ota-onalarining roziligi mavjud bo'lgan va tibbiy hujjatlari to'liq qayd etilgan bemorlar kiritildi. Jarayon va ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlashda yosh, jins, tashxis va antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar inobatga olindi. Perinatal zararlanish tashxisi bolalarning shifoxonaga yotqizilishidan oldin mutaxassis shifokorlar tomonidan tasdiqlangan edi. Ishtirokchilar kasallik turiga qarab quyidagilarga ajratildi: serebral falaj, neyral naycha nuqsonlari, genetik kasalliklar, neyromuskulyar patologiyalar, metabolik sindromlar, epileptik holatlar va toksik ensefalopatiya. Keyinchalik bu guruhlar quyidagi asosiy toifalarga birlashtirildi: - progressiv ensefalopatiya (2,4%), - progressiv bo'lmagan ensefalopatiya (87,8%), - neyromuskulyar kasalliklar (9,8%). Antropometrik o'Ichovlar Antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar standart usullar orqali qayd etildi: tana vazni, bo'yi va bosh atrofi o'Ichandi. So'ngra tana massasi indeksi (BMI) hamda bosh atrofi/bo'y nisbati (HCI) hisoblab chiqildi. Barcha ko'rsatkichlar uchun z-ballar aniqlanib, me'yoriy qiymatlar bilan solishtirildi.

Baholash mezonlari - Bosh atrofi: normal, mikrosefaliya yoki makrosefaliya. - Bo'y uzunligi: normal, past bo'y, baland bo'y. - Ovqatlanish holati: normal, vazn yetishmovchiligi, ortiqcha vazn yoki semizlik. - Harakat qobiliyati: GMFCS mezonlari asosida baholanib, yengil, o'rta va og'ir darajalarga ajratildi.

Natijalar: Tadqiqot guruhiga kiritilgan 110 nafar bolaning o'rtacha yoshi 1 yosh bo'lib, yosh diapazoni 1 oylikdan 2 yoshgacha edi. Ularning 56,3 foizi o'g'il bolalar, 43,7 foizi esa qiz bolalar edi.

Jinsiy tarkib

Antropometrik natijalar - Bo'y uzunligi: Bolalarning taxminan beshdan bir qismida bo'y me'yoridan past, 8 foizga yaqinida esa ortiqcha balandlik kuzatildi. Qolganlarida ko'rsatkich

me'yorida edi. - Tana vazni: Ishtirokchilarning 14,6 foizida vazn yetishmovchiligi, 6,8 foizida esa ortiqcha vazn yoki semizlik qayd etildi.

Antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar

Bosh atrofi: 12,5 foizida mikrocefaliya, 9,7 foizida makrocefaliya kuzatildi. Qolganlarida bosh atrofi me'yoriy chegarada edi. Harakat faoliyati Harakat qobiliyati GMFCS mezonlari asosida o'lganida, ishtirokchilarning qariyb uchdan ikki qismida yengil yoki o'rtada darajadagi cheklanish, qolgan qismida esa og'ir buzilishlar aniqlandi. Perinatal ensefalopatiya va serebral falaj tashxisi qo'yilgan bolalarda harakat qobiliyati buzilishlari eng ko'p kuzatildi. Tizimli bog'liqliklar O'tkazilgan statistik tahlillar natijasida quyidagi bog'liqliklar aniqlandi: - Mikrocefaliya kuzatilgan bolalarda ko'pincha past bo'y va vazn yetishmovchiligi qayd etildi. - Makrocefaliya bo'lganlarda baland bo'y va ortiqcha vazn kuzatilish ehtimoli yuqori bo'ldi. - Harakat qobiliyatining og'ir buzilishi antropometrik ko'rsatkichlarning normadan og'ishi bilan chambarchas bog'liq edi. Qo'shimcha kuzatuvlar Neyromuskulyar kasalliklarga ega bolalarda tana vazni va bo'y orasidagi nomutanosibliklar tez-tez uchradi. Genetik kasalliklarga ega ishtirokchilarda esa mikrocefaliya va past bo'y ustunlik qildi.

Muhokama: Olingan ma'lumotlar shuni anglatadiki, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi bolalarda nafaqat nevrologik sindromlar, balki jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlariga ham bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Tadqiqot ishtirokchilarining muayyan qismida past bo'y, vazn yetishmovchiligi va bosh atrofi bilan bog'liq anomalialar qayd etildi. Bu esa perinatal davrda yuzaga kelgan shikastlanishlar bola organizmining keyingi o'sishi va rivojlanishini sekinlashtirishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Mikrocefaliya kuzatilgan bolalarda past bo'y va vazn yetishmovchiligi ustunlik qildi. Aksincha, makrocefaliya bo'lgan ishtirokchilarda baland bo'y va ortiqcha vazn ko'proq qayd etildi. Ushbu kuzatuvlar organizmning gormonal va metabolik jarayonlari bilan bog'liq bo'lishi ehtimolini ko'rsatadi. Harakat faoliyatining buzilishi, xususan og'ir darajadagi cheklanishlar, perinatal ensefalopatiya va serebral falaj tashxisi qo'yilgan bolalarda ko'proq uchradi. Bu esa somatik rivojlanishdagi nomutanosibliklarni yanada kuchaytiruvchi omil bo'lishi mumkin.

1- Jadval. Markaziy asab tizimi perinatal zararlanishiga ega bolalarning antropometrik va funksional ko'rsatkichlari

Ko'rsatkich	Kuzatilgan holatlar	Foiz (%)	Izoh
Bo'y uzunligi	Me'yordan past	20	Mikrocefaliyasi bor bolalarda ko'p uchradi
	Me'yorda	72	Makrocefaliyalı bolalarda kuzatildi

	Me'yordan yuqori	8	Neyromuskulyar buzilishli bolalarda ustun
Tana vazni	Vazn yetishmovchiligi	14,6	Asosan sog'lom rivojlanishdagi bolalar
	Me'yorda	78,6	Asosiy qism
	Ortiqcha vazn / semizlik	6,8	Makrofefaliya bilan bog'liq holatlar
Bosh atrofi	Mikrofefaliya	12,5	Past bo'y va vazn yetishmovchiligi bilan bog'liq
	Me'yorda	77,8	Normal rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlari
	Makrofefaliya	9,7	Baland bo'y va ortiqcha vazn bilan bog'liq
Harakat faoliyati	Yengil / o'rta darajadagi buzilishlar	66	Asosan perinatal ensefalopatiya holatlarida
	Og'ir darajadagi buzilishlar	34	Serebral falaj bilan bog'liq
Qo'shimcha kuzatuvlar	Neyromuskulyar kasalliklar	—	Bo'y va vazn orasida nomutanosiblik
	Genetik sindromlar	—	Mikrofefaliya va past bo'y ustunlik qildi

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi bo'lgan bolalarda jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlarida sezilarli farqlar mavjud. Mikrofefaliya ko'pincha past bo'y va vazn yetishmovchiligi bilan birga kechgan, makrofefaliya esa ortiqcha bo'y va tana vazni bilan bog'liq bo'lgan. Harakat faoliyatining og'ir buzilishi antropometrik og'ishlar bilan chambarchas bog'langan.

Bir qator ilmiy manbalarda ham perinatal ensefalopatiya va neyromuskulyar kasalliklarga chalingan bolalarda rivojlanishning sekinlashuvi, ovqatlanish bilan bog'liq muammolar va bosh atrofi anomaliyalari keng tarqalganligi qayd etilgan. Patologiyani erta aniqlash va doimiy kuzatib borish uning oqibatlarini yumshatishda asosiy omil hisoblanadi. Neonatologlar, pediatrlar va nevrologlarning yaqin hamkorligi esa bolalarning hayot sifatini yaxshilash uchun muhimdir.

Xulosa: Olingan natijalar shuni anglatadiki, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi bolalarda o'sish va rivojlanish jarayoniga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ko'plab ishtirokchilarda bosh atrofi o'zgarishlari, tana vazni va bo'y uzunligidagi nomutanosibliklar kuzatildi. Ayniqsa, og'ir harakat cheklanishiga ega bolalarda somatik rivojlanish buzilishlari ko'proq qayd etildi. Kasallikni erta aniqlash hamda bolalarni muntazam kuzatib borish ularning keyingi rivojlanishi uchun asosiy omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan birga, rehabilitatsiya dasturlarini to'g'ri tashkil etish bolalarning kundalik faoliyati va ijtimoiy integratsiyasini yengillashtiradi. Shunday qilib, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi bo'lgan bolalarni pediatr, nevrolog va boshqa mutaxassislar tomonidan tizimli ravishda kuzatish tavsiya etiladi.

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